

Media: RhMix

Description: Developed by Kristen Hunter-Cevera as a replete minimal media for the oleaginous yeast *Rhodospiridium toruloides* to investigate C:N ratios. Media recipe is a combination and interpolation of several different artificial seawater recipes coupled with standard yeast recipes as benchmarks of macronutrients and vitamin concentrations (see below resources).

Components	Amount	Final conc in media	Notes
DI Water	800 mL	----	
NaCl	2.805 g	48 mM	
KH ₂ PO ₄	13.61 g	100 mM	
NH ₄ Cl	8.89 g	166.23 mM	
PIPES disodium salt	17.3165 g	50 mM	pH to 7.0
Glucose soln.	100 mL	166.52 mM	add after autoclaving
MgSO ₄ solution	5 mL	6 mM	add after autoclaving
CaCl ₂ solution	1 mL	2 mM	add after autoclaving
H ₃ BO ₃ solution	1 mL	84 μM	add after autoclaving
Trace metal soln.	1mL	see recipe	add after autoclaving
Vitamin solution 1	1 mL	see recipe	add after autoclaving
Vitamin solution 2	1 mL	see recipe	add after autoclaving
Vitamin solution 3	100 μL	see recipe	add after autoclaving

To make media, add NaCl, KH₂PO₄, and NH₄Cl as indicated to water. Allow to dissolve. Add PIPES salt. Adjust pH to ~7.0 with 1 M NaOH and bring total volume to 890 mL with DI water.

Sterilize by autoclaving at 121 °C for 30 min. Allow to cool to room temperature. Add sugar, salts, trace metal, and vitamin solutions aseptically in laminar flow hood. Store at 4 °C. Watch for precipitation (this will happen, but disperses enough at room temperature).

Notes: If using in bioreactor with pH control, omit PIPES buffer and adjust to desired starting pH. Current formulation is for N-replete (or C:N = 6). For N-limitation, 1.78 g NH₄Cl will yield C:N = 30.

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Salt / sugar stock solutions

Solution	Amount	Water	Stock conc.	Final conc in media
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	29.5764 g	100 mL	1.2 M	6 mM
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	14.701 g	100 mL	1 M	2 mM
H ₃ BO ₃	0.5193 g	100 mL	84 mM	84 μM
Glucose	30 g	100 mL	1.665 M	166.52 mM

For each solution, add reagent to water and dissolve. Sterilize by autoclave for salts. For glucose solution, sterilization by filtration is recommended to avoid caramelization.

Trace metal solution

For ease of addition, metals require individual stock solutions to be made first before addition to combined trace metal stock solution.

Individual stock solutions:

	Amount	Water	Indiv. stock conc
CuSO ₄ · 5H ₂ O	0.499 g	50 mL	40 mM
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	5.751 g	50 mL	400 mM
CoCl ₂ · 6H ₂ O	1.189 g	50 mL	100 mM
Na ₂ MoO ₄ · 2H ₂ O	0.726 g	50 mL	60 mM
MnCl ₄ · 4H ₂ O	15.212 g	50 mL	1.537 M
Na ₂ SeO ₃	0.8648 g	50 mL	100 mM
NiCl · 6H ₂ O	1.1884 g	50 mL	100 mM

Weigh out each reagent. Dissolve in 50 mL in Falcon tube. Store at -20 °C. Use in below trace metal solution.

Trace metal stock solution:

	Amount per 100 mL	Stock Conc	Conc in media
Na ₂ EDTA · 2H ₂ O	6.7242 g	0.2 M	200 µM
FeCl ₃ · 6H ₂ O	5.4058 g	0.2 M	200 µM
MnCl ₄ · stock	5 mL	90 mM	90 µM
CuSO ₄ · stock	5 mL	2 mM	2 µM
ZnSO ₄ · stock	5 mL	20 mM	20 µM
CoCl ₂ · stock	5 mL	5 mM	5 µM
Na ₂ MoO ₄ · stock	5 mL	3 mM	3 µM
Na ₂ SeO ₃ · stock	5 mL	5 mM	5 µM
NiCl · stock	5 mL	5 mM	5 µM

Directions: Weigh out Na₂EDTA · 2H₂O and add to flask with 50 mL of dH₂O. Next, weigh out FeCl₃ · 6H₂O and add to flask, inverting to dissolve. Add metal stock solutions, one at a time, making sure each is dissolved before the next is added. Add water until volume is 100 mL. Filter-sterilize solution and store at 4 °C.

Vitamin solutions

Some of these also require individual stock solutions to be made ahead of time:

Component	Amount	Diluent	Indiv. stock conc
Riboflavin / B2	50 mg	20 mL DMSO	2500 mg/L
Biotin / B7	50 mg	10 mL DMSO	5000 mg/ L
Folic Acid / B9	100 mg	10 mL DMSO	10000 mg/L
Cyanocobalamin / B12	50 mg	50 mL DI water	1000 mg/ L
4-Aminobenzoic acid / PABA	500 mg	500 mL DI water	1000 mg/L

Directions: Weigh out each reagent. Dissolve into specified substance and volume. Riboflavin solution must be gently heated (~60 °C for an hour to dissolve). Folic acid also takes awhile to dissolve in DMSO at room temperature.

Notes: Riboflavin, folic acid and biotin are essentially insoluble in water at neutral pH. PABA is soluble, but this appears to be the maximum dissolvable concentration. The above stocks are from a few rounds of trial and error with different volumes and solvents.

Vitamin stock solutions:

	Indiv. stock conc	Amount added	Total Stock conc.	Final conc. in media	Notes
Vitamin Solution 1: to 100 mL H ₂ O					
Calcium pantothenate /B4	----	400 mg	4000 mg/L	4 mg/L	
Inositol	---	2 g	20000 mg/L	20 mg/L	
Niacin / B3	---	400 mg	4000 mg/L	4 mg/L	
Vitamin Solution 2: to 100 mL H ₂ O					
Thiamin HCl / B1	---	500 mg	5000 mg/L	5 mg/L	
Pyridoxine-HCl / B5		250 mg	2500 mg/L	2.5 mg/L	
4-Aminobenzoic acid / PABA	1000 mg/L	50 mL	500 mg /L	0.5 mg/L	
Cyanocobalamin / B12	1000 mg/ L	5 mL	50 mg/L	0.05 mg/L	
Vitamin Solution 3: to 10 mL DMSO					
Biotin / B7	5000 mg/ L	1 mL	500 mg/L	0.05 mg/L	Dissolved in DMSO
Riboflavin / B2	2500 mg/L	1 mL	250 mg/L	0.025 mg/L	Dissolved in DMSO
Folic Acid / B9	10000 mg/L	1 mL	1000 mg/L	0.1 mg/L	Dissolved in DMSO

For each solution, weigh out reagent or add stock solutions to water or DMSO. Adjust to final volume. Filter sterilize and store at 4 °C. Note: filtration of DMSO solutions requires nylon filter.